

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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INSON DUNYOQARASHNING SHAKLLANISHDA MA'NAVIYATNING O'RNI.

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Kalit so'zlar: Dunyoqarash, tafakkur, ijtimoiy ong, mafkura, ma'naviyat, islohot, umuminsoniy qadriyatlar, milliy qadriyatlar, plyuralizm.

Annotatsiya: Inson hayotida, kishilik taraqqiyotida ma'naviyatning o'rni benihoya kattadir. Ma'naviyatga har bir zamonda har bir davrda ehtiyoj sezilgan bo'lib u insonning kamolotida shaxs bo'lib shakllanishida ma'naviyat botiniy kuchdir.

Insonda dunyoqarash, tafakkur va ijtimoiy ong shakllarning yuksalishi jamiyatga uyushib yashash zaruriyatining natijasida shakllandi va u o'zining atrofidagi muhitga, inson va insoniy munosabatlarga zaruriyat seza boshladi. Natijada insonda ma'naviyat-ma'rifiy dunyoqarash shakllandi. Ma'naviyat faqat tarixiy va an'anaviy qadriyatlar yig'indisi bo'lmay, insonning yashash shakli bilan uyg'unlashib bir-birini to'ldirib boruvchi voqelikdir. Ma'naviyatning shakllanishiga oid turli davrlarda turli xil fikrlar mavjud bo'lib ularning aksariyati o'tmishdagi voqeliklarga mutanosib shaklda shakllangan. Aksariyat olimlar ma'naviyatga doir o'z izlanishlarini faqat o'tmish bilan cheklaydilar, hozirgi kunning dolzarb maqsad va vazifalari bilan bog'lamaydilar. Hozirgi davrga kelib rivojlangan mamlakatlarda fuqarolik jamiyati qadriyatlari xalq hokimiyati, hokimiyatning fuqarolar manfaatlarini asosida faoliyat yuritishini, siyosiy qarorlar qabul qilishni ko'pchilik inson ovozi bilan hal etish, ozchilik huquqlarining hurmat qilinishi, asosiy huquqlarini amal qilinishiga kafolatlar yaratilganligi, erkin va adolatli saylovlar tizimini an'anaga aylanganligi, qonunning barcha uchun tengligi, odil sud hokimiyatining o'rnatilishi, dunyoqarashlar plyuralizmi, turli xil qarashlar va fikrlarning o'zaro bir-biriga bag'ri keng bo'lishi kabi qadriyatlar har bir jamiyat a'zosining ma'naviyati va madaniyatining uzviy va ajralmas bo'laklariga aylandi. Bugun mamlakatimiz

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o'z oldiga rivojlangan mamlakatlar ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy taraqqiyoti darajasiga erishishni maqsad qilib qo'ygan bo'lib, yangi O'zbekiston jamiyati qurishdek ezgu maqsadlar sari ildamlamoqda. Har bir millat va xalqlar tarixida shunday yangilanish vaqtlari davri borki, bunday davrda millatning ezgulikka intilishi, ixtiro va kashfiyotlari yuksak cho'qqilarga ko'tarishi bilan baholanadi. Anashunday ezgu maqsadlar mushtarakligiga nafaqat hozirgi zamonda balki har bir zamonda ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar yetakchi rol o'ynagan. Bunday jarayonlarda tinchlik va osoyishtalikni asrash, jahon hamjamiyatida o'ziga xos va munosib o'rni bor davlat sifatida, ajdodlarimiz merosini chuqur o'rganish bilan birga, ushbu an'analarni yanada yuksakroqqa ko'tarish zarurati mavjud. Ma'naviyatni rivojlantirishning eng asosiy maqsadlaridan biri –mamlakatimizda amalga oshirilayotgan keng ko'lamlil islohotlarni jamiyatimizning barcha azolari barcha qatlamlarining ong-u shuuriga qalbiga yetib borishini ularda yuksak fuqarolik pozitsiyasini shakllantirishni, Vatani yurti taqdiriga befarq bo'lmagan yoshlarni tarbiyalashdir. Mamlakatda yangi jamiyat qurish va uni rivojlantirish maqsadlarida, birinchi o'rinda, inson omiliga muhim e'tibor berish, ma'naviy yuksak insonlarni shakllantirish davlat siyosatining muhim yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Shuning uchun ham jamiyatda yashaydigan barcha fuqarolarning milliy va ma'naviy qadriyatlar kabi asosiy maqsadlar atrofida birlashishi va jipslashishi ular faoliyatini yanada takomillashtiradi. Insoniyat yaratilgan eng qadimgi davrdan boshlab to bugungi kungacha bo'lgan davrda, hayotiy va insoniy qulayliklarga ega bo'lgan adolatli jamiyat qurishga intilishlar hamon davom etmoqda. Tarixning ilk davridanoq adolatli jamiyat qurishda jamiyat barqarorligini saqlashning bebaho omili sifatida axloqiy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarni rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratgan. Aynan ana shu asos tufayli ideal jamiyat orzusidagi tasavvurlarga oid ilmiy, ijtimoiy-falsafiy va diniy qarashlar shakllandi. Milliy ma'naviyatimiz tarixida o'chmas iz qoldirgan buyuk allomalarimiz, mutafakkir bobolarimizning Vatan va xalq oldidagi xizmatlari, bebaho ilmiy va ijodiy merosi bilan nafaqat xalqimizni, ayni vaqtda dunyo jamoatchiligini ham keng tanishtirishga alohida ahamiyat berilmoqda. Ma'lumki, Markaziy Osiyo zamini islom ilm-fani va madaniyatining qadimiy beshiklaridan biri hisoblanadi. Xalqimizning boy tarixiy, ilmiy, ma'naviy

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merosini har tomonlama o'rganish, islom dinining asl insonparvarlik mohiyatini chuqur ochib berish «Jaholatga qarshi –ma'rifat» tamoyili asosida ma'naviy qadriyatlarimizni asrash bu sohadagi islohotlar negizidir. Xalqaro maydonda mafkuraviy manzarani o'zgarib borayotganligi, jahon siyosati va iqtisodida muammolar avj olayotganligi dunyoning umumiy manzarasini o'zgartirish tarafdorlari ko'payib borayotganligi global dunyo taraqqiyotiga xos bo'lgan eng muhim xususiyatlar sifatida namoyon bo'lmoqda. Chunonchi, "shunday bir vaziyatda jamiyatimizni ma'naviy tahdidlardan himoya qilish borasidagi ilmiy-amaliy tadqiqotlarni, tahliliy va targ'ibot materiallarini tayyorlash usulini tubdan qayta ko'rib chiqishimiz zarur. Umuminsoniy, milliy va diniy qadriyatlarimizga bepisandlik bilan qarash holatlariga qarshi kurashishning metodologik asoslarini shakllantirish lozim" Ijtimoiy hayotimizda ko'plab ijobiy jarayonlar bilan birga, yosh avlodning qalbi va ongini egallashga qaratilgan ma'naviy tahdidlar ham tobora xavfli tus olmoqda. Yoshlarimizni ona Vatanimizga, mustaqillik g'oyalariga muhabbat va sadoqat ruhida tarbiyalash, ularning iste'dod va qobiliyatini, ezgu intilishlarini ro'yobga chiqarish yo'lida Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy jihatlaridan foydalanish ayni muddao. Zamonaviy ilm-fan va yuqori texnologiyalarni mukammal egallash har qanday davlat va jamiyat taraqqiyotining hal qiluvchi omiliga aylandi. Yoshlarni ilmiy va innovatsion faoliyatga keng jalb etish, yosh olimlarning innovatsion faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashga katta e'tibor berilmoqda. Shiddat bilan o'zgarib, barqarorlik va millatlar xavfsizligiga rahna soladigan turli taxdid va xatarlar kuchayayotgan kunda ma'naviyat va ma'rifatga, g'oya va mafkura jarayonlariga alohida diqqat qaratish muhimdir.

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